
LIBRARY MOBILE APPLICATION

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Abstract:

Now a days Mobile phones have become the essential part of human life for communication, different sectors like banks, financial institutions, government sectors, marketing industries are providing their service via mobile apps to benefit their users and it also helps to student in e-learning. Mobile Technology will be of great help to libraries. It will be also helpful to librarians to provide better library services through mobile phone to the users. This paper presents brief introduction about the Mobile application technology and its use in library services and challenges in library services with help of mobile devices, libraries can produce new services and provide faster access to its collection.

Keywords: *Mobile Technology, Library services*

Introduction:

The mobile app usage has significantly changed the way that people interact with the information and the way they view a library. There are number of existing library mobile application, through which various libraries are providing different services Mobile Technology has activated the Connection between library Services and its users. Libraries are always ready to adopt new recent technologies like OPAC, RFID, and Bar Code System for books & also users etc. The traditional library services are now moving to mobile library information services Mobile technologies have made communication and information access very convenient and timely to users. Library and Information Science professionals are no more merely caretakers of books. They do the challenging, non-commercial business of satisfying information needs of users.

A library mobile app is a benefit for both the librarians and the patrons. Mobile phones are essential tool for everyone for information communication purpose. Application of mobile phones to provide library and information services will open new pathway towards this trend. For this purpose, the use of technology is very essential. It can provide a wide array of library services to your patrons. Using a mobile app they can check due dates, place a hold, renew a book, and even get alerts when books are due or hold become available.

Mobile Library Services:

- 1. Wi-Fi Internet Access:** Mobile phones are available with 4G facility. Libraries can offer Wi-Fi facility to users.
- 2. SMS Alert Service:** Library automations Software provide option to send SMS form reserved

books, book return book issue to the users. Also reminding the user if books is due. Library opening & Closing hours. New Arrivals in the Library. Give alerts on latest news, events, and notices via SMS or MMS to users wherever they might be going. Owners may be need to download these applications themselves. There are several apps available such as text messaging, Skype, What's app, Yahoo and Facebook

3. **Reference Service:** Ask a librarian service can be given through chat, e - mail and even through call by using phone dialing feature.
4. **Suggest And Purchase:** Librarian can receive the suggestions from the users via mobile phones. In such cases users need not to visit the libraries and write the requirements in a register.
5. **Digital Card:** Eliminate the need of physical card, risk of loss or misuse. Barcode/QR code on card can be scanned. User can simply carry card in their mobile phones.
6. **Library Virtual Tours:** Audio Video tours of library can be produce to new users of library. It is fairly quickly, inexpensively, and could reduce the amount staff time spent helping new users to orient themselves in the library and explaining the facilities available The library users, who don't have time can get access to library tours on their mobile devices.
7. **OPAC on Mobile Phones:** User can easily search library OPAC to know the status of available resources. Allowing patrons to search for books, e-resources etc. at single platform.
8. **Request:** Remote renewal, reservation, book recommendation, requests can be raised through mobile app being at remote location.
9. **News:** New arrivals, bulletin board, library digest, news clippings options can be integrated. Information on job openings, varieties of scholarly competition, library events
10. **E –Resources:** Personalized setting for bookshelf of favorite e-books and e- journals can also be integrated.
11. **Event Calendar:** Integrated event calendar for notifying library events and activities through e-mail or push notification.
12. **Payment Gateway:** Direct gateway for fine or fee payment integrated in mobile app.
13. **Social Media:** User can view library's social account directly from mobile app.
14. **About Library:** Users can access library guides and library tutorials from their smart phones. Easy navigation to information about library, rules, timings, holidays etc.
15. **User Account:** User can check their accounts, late fee, overdue, history etc. Which books he used.
16. **Research Consultation and Instruction:** Library staff provides reference service to researchers through mobile phones. Many publishers are crating e-books, e-magazines, etc. which are compatible with the mobile devices so that users can easily access and read them.
17. **Journal Finder:** Library Journal Finder provides access to full text journal, magazine, and newspaper content.
18. **Reference Service:** Library users can ask librarians anything through the live chat and texting with mobiles. Immediate feedback is also possible from the user side.

19. Marketing Of Library Services:

Mobile Technology used as Marketing of Library Products; Library resources / services, E-Resources, Rare book Collection Libraries can reach the users directly through their mobiles and apply its marketing.

Advantages of Library Services on**Mobile:**

1. User-friendly Aid
2. 24x7 access
3. User Participation
4. Time and cost economy
5. Limitless Access
6. Ability to Access Information
7. Personalized Service
8. Location Awareness

Disadvantages of Library Services on**Mobile:**

1. Limited memory of Mobile Phone.
2. Low internet connectivity problem
3. Lack of trained staff
4. Power capacity
5. Size of mobile screen is small as compare to PC.

Conclusion:

Human beings in a society use mobile phone to communicate thoughts, facts, conversations, in general, information. Implementing the Mobile App to Improve Library Services is a very effective way to disseminate the library information products and services online. Mobile applications are much easier to use and provide better user experience than websites. Libraries can also analyze user activity for better user experience and future updates and modifications. Despite a few limitations, mobile applications are beneficial in the long run-in mass communication. This is a good time for Library & Information Professionals to embrace new and innovative technologies

References:

1. <http://crln.acrl.org/content/72/4/22>
2. <http://www.americanlibrariesmagazine.org/article/libraries-and-mobile-services>
3. <http://www.inflibnet.ac.in/caliber2009/CaliberPDF/33>.
4. <http://jalis.in/pdf/6-4/Gaik.pdf>
5. <http://www.slideshare.net/KatieSee/ler/mobile-technology-and-the-academic-library>
6. <http://www.thehindu.com/sci-tech/technology/internet/internet-mobile-users-set-to-double-to-165-m-by-2015/article4265560.ece>